

Hexadecanoic Acid as a Potential Anxiolytic Agent: In Silico Insights Targeting the 5-HT_{1B} Receptor

(Ácido hexadecanoico como um potencial agente ansiolítico: insights in silico direcionados ao receptor 5-HT_{1B})

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RESUMO

O ácido hexadecanoico (AH), também conhecido como ácido palmítico, é um ácido graxo saturado amplamente presente na dieta humana, com possíveis efeitos neuromoduladores ainda pouco explorados. Este estudo avaliou o potencial ansiolítico do AH utilizando abordagens *in silico*, investigando sua interação com o receptor serotoninérgico 5-HT_{1B}, um alvo terapêutico relevante em transtornos de ansiedade. O software HEX 8.0.0 foi utilizado para simulações de docking molecular, com validação do protocolo por um novo docking para fluoxetina, um fármaco antagonista clássico deste receptor, amplamente utilizado pelo Sistema Único de Saúde (SUS) no Brasil. As análises estruturais foram realizadas utilizando o software PyMOL 1.4.7 e o Biovia Discovery Studio® 2021. Os resultados indicaram que o AH possui afinidade significativa pelo sítio ativo do receptor 5-HT_{1B}, estabelecendo interações hidrofóbicas e de van der Waals com resíduos-chave, semelhantes às da fluoxetina. Esses achados sugerem que o AH pode atuar como um modulador da atividade serotoninérgica e justificam estudos experimentais adicionais para avaliar seu efeito ansiolítico em modelos animais.

ABSTRACT

Hexadecanoic acid (HA), also known as palmitic acid, is a saturated fatty acid widely present in the human diet, with possible neuromodulatory effects still little explored. This study evaluated the anxiolytic potential of HA using *in silico* approaches, investigating its interaction with the 5-HT_{1B} serotonin receptor, a relevant therapeutic target in anxiety disorders. The HEX 8.0.0 software was used for molecular docking simulations, with validation of the protocol by a new docking for fluoxetine, a classic antagonist drug of this receptor, widely used by the Unified Health System (SUS) in Brazil. Structural analyses were performed using PyMOL 1.4.7 software and Biovia Discovery Studio® 2021. The results indicated that HA has significant affinity for the active site of the 5-HT_{1B} receptor, establishing hydrophobic and van der Waals interactions with key residues, similar to those of fluoxetine. These findings suggest that HA may act as a modulator of serotonergic activity and justify further experimental studies to evaluate its anxiolytic effect in animal models.

INTRODUÇÃO / INTRODUCTION

Depression and anxiety are highly prevalent psychiatric disorders that often coexist and negatively impact individuals' psychological well-being and functionality.¹ Depression, in particular, has been associated with persistent neurochemical alterations and is projected to become one of the leading causes of global disability by 2030, according to the World Health Organization (WHO).² Anxiety, in turn, is characterized by restlessness, excessive worry and physiological symptoms that affect the stress response and cognition.³

Throughout history, traditional medicine has been widely used to treat various health conditions.^{4,5,6} In the search for more effective and safer treatments, traditional medicine and compounds of natural origin have been gaining prominence. The use of medicinal plants and natural derivatives represents an important source of bioactive molecules with pharmacological properties, including anxiolytic and antidepressant action.⁸ Herbal compounds have shown promise due to their accessibility, lower toxicity and greater acceptance among patients, in addition to offering a diversity of biological mechanisms of action.^{8,9,10}

Among the dietary compounds that have been arousing interest in the scientific community is hexadecanoic acid (HA), also known as palmitic acid. This saturated fatty acid is widely consumed in the human diet and is present in foods such as meat, dairy products, vegetable oils (such as palm oil) and industrialized products. Although its excess is often associated with adverse effects such as insulin resistance, dyslipidemia and chronic inflammation, recent studies have explored its impact on brain function and mental health.¹¹

Emerging literature indicates that the lipid profile of the diet can directly influence synaptic plasticity, neurogenesis and neurotransmission. Diets rich in saturated fatty acids, such as HA, can modulate inflammatory and metabolic pathways in the brain, affecting the function of receptors such as GABA, NMDA and serotonergic receptors. Some studies suggest that chronic consumption of saturated fats can impair cognition and increase vulnerability to stress, while others point out that certain fatty acids play a modulating role, participating in neuronal signaling and maintaining the integrity of the blood-brain barrier.^{12,13}

Specifically, palmitic acid has been investigated for its ability to interact with neurotransmitter systems involved in emotional regulation. It is known that fatty acids can act as precursors of lipid mediators that regulate inflammation and synaptic function, as well as participating in the structural composition of neuronal membranes. These properties raise the hypothesis that HA, despite its controversial metabolic effects, may also have a neuroactive action with therapeutic implications for mood disorders.

Thus, this study aims to evaluate, through *in silico* approaches, the potential of hexadecanoic acid as a modulator of the 5-HT_{1B} serotonergic receptor - a pharmacological target widely associated with the regulation of anxiety. The identification of relevant molecular interactions can contribute to the understanding of nutritional mechanisms associated with mental

health and stimulate pre-clinical and clinical investigations into the functional role of dietary components in neuropsychiatry.

METODOLOGIA / METHODS

In silico experimentation

Obtaining and preparing molecules

The three-dimensional (3D) conformers of the compounds hexadecanoic acid (PubChem CID: 22311) and fluoxetine (PubChem CID: 3386) were obtained in SDF format from the PubChem chemical database (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>).¹⁴ The two-dimensional (2D) structures of the respective ligands are illustrated in Figure 1 for visual representation purposes.

Figure 1. Molecular docking between hexadecanoic acid and the 5-HT_{1B} receptor. **Source:** Author

The 5-HT_{1B} serotonin receptor (PDB ID: 5V54), widely implicated in the pathophysiology of depression, was selected as the target protein. The crystallographic structure of the protein was obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB). Before the simulations, the protein was prepared by removing water molecules and co-crystallized ligands, if present, and structural optimization using Biovia Discovery Studio® 2021 software.

Molecular docking protocol

Molecular docking simulations between the ligands (hexadecanoic acid and fluoxetine) and the 5-HT_{1B} receptor were conducted using the HEX software (version 8.0.0),¹⁵ with support for visualization and analysis via PyMol (version 1.4.7)¹⁶ and Biovia Discovery Studio® 2021, on a 64-bit operating system. 50,000 simulations were carried out for each ligand, with the 10 best poses selected based on the interaction energy. The validity of the protocol was verified through an additional simulation with fluoxetine as a positive control. Analysis of the complexes formed considered aspects such as hydrophobic interactions, hydrogen bonds and binding energy, with graphical representation in PyMol and Discovery Studio.

RESULTADOS E DISCUSSÃO / RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Molecular docking

The similarity in binding site occupancy suggests that HA may modulate receptor activity in a similar way to fluoxetine, an antidepressant widely used in clinical practice.¹⁷ This finding reinforces the reliability of the computational protocol used, which was previously validated through a new docking of fluoxetine. The interaction of the ligands with the 5-HT_{1B} receptor is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Three-dimensional representation of the complex formed between the 5-HT_{1B} receptor (pink cartoon) and the ligands: fluoxetine (orange sticks) and hexadecanoic acid (purple sticks), showing overlap at the same binding site. **Source:** Author

In a complementary way, previous studies with Benzyloxyamine¹⁷ also demonstrated affinity and specificity for the same binding site as fluoxetine in the 5-HT₁ receptor, with the formation of multiple chemical bonds with residues such as Val-233, Glu-234 and Thr-209. This convergence between different compounds in relation to the same target reinforces the pharmacological relevance of the 5-HT_{1B} receptor. Similar results were observed with Terpinene,¹⁸ a terpene compound of plant origin, which established nine relevant interactions with the 5-HT₁ receptor, recruiting residues such as Val-233, Ile-206, Ala-226 and Pro-338.

The partial overlap of these residues with those observed in the interactions of hexadecanoic acid reinforces the hypothesis that different natural compounds - even with different chemical structures - can functionally converge on the same 5-HT_{1B} receptor binding site. These findings support the pharmacological relevance of this receptor in the modulation of anxiety and strengthen the applicability of *in silico* approaches as predictive tools in the screening of bioactive candidates of natural origin.

Analysis of the interactions revealed that HA recruits several amino acid residues to the receptor's active site, including: Ile39, Tyr40, Tyr109, Leu348, Asp352, Cys199, Val199, Val200, Trp125, Leu126, Val201, Thr355, Tyr359, Phe330, Asp129,

Cys133, Trp327, Ile130, Ala216, Thr134 and Phe331. These interactions mainly involve van der Waals forces and hydrophobic interactions, which are recognized as fundamental for the stability of the ligand-receptor complex (Figure 3). The presence of hydrophobic residues in the binding site, such as valine and leucine, reinforces the importance of hydrophobic interactions in stabilizing the complex, which is in line with the lipophilic nature of HA.¹⁹

Figure 3. Two-dimensional diagram of the chemical interactions between HA and the 5-HT_{1B} receptor, highlighting the participating residues. On the right, 3D visualization of active site binding. **Source:** Author

The occupation of the binding site by HA suggests that this fatty acid may influence the conformation of the 5-HT_{1B} receptor, possibly modulating its activity and, consequently, serotonergic neurotransmission.^{18,20} This effect may have implications for the treatment of conditions related to the serotonergic system, such as anxiety, since modulation of this receptor is an established therapeutic target.^{17, 21} In addition, hydrophobicity analysis indicated that HA interacts favorably with hydrophobic regions of the receptor, which may contribute to the stability of the complex.¹⁹ This hydrophobic compatibility may be associated with the predominant presence of apolar residues, such as Val, Ile and Leu, at the binding interface.

From a functional point of view, these results suggest that HA has the potential to modulate the activity of the 5-HT_{1B} receptor, indicating a possible anxiolytic effect. This hypothesis is strengthened by studies linking fatty acids with the regulation of neurotransmitters and cognitive functions.²² Although HA is widely known for its structural and energetic role, few studies address its direct neuromodulatory effects, which makes this finding relevant and innovative in the context of neuropharmacology. Additionally, considering that other fatty acids - such as oleic acid and linoleic acid^{23, 24} - have been associated with effects on the central nervous system, it is recommended that future studies include comparisons between different classes of fatty acids in order to assess selectivity and relative efficacy on the same molecular target.²⁵

The identification of the affinity between HA and the 5-HT_{1B} receptor provides a promising basis for future *in vivo* trials,

especially in behavioral models of anxiety. Considering its natural presence in the diet, the translational potential of HA as a nutraceutical compound or complementary agent in mental health stands out. To deepen the understanding of the interaction mechanisms, molecular dynamics simulations are recommended, as they can provide data on the temporal stability of the complexes, conformational fluctuations and binding free energy (ΔG). Finally, the results presented here justify *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies to confirm the functional activity of HA on the 5-HT_{1B} receptor and assess whether the physiological effects match the *in silico* predictions.

CONCLUSÕES / CONCLUSIONS

The results of this *in silico* study indicate that hexadecanoic acid (HA) has affinity and specificity for the 5-HT_{1B} receptor, sharing the same binding site as fluoxetine and forming stable interactions with relevant amino acid residues. This evidence suggests that HA may act as a modulator of serotonergic activity, possibly exerting anxiolytic effects. The hydrophobic compatibility observed reinforces its stability in the ligand-receptor complex, highlighting the neuromodulatory potential of this saturated fatty acid widely present in the diet. Thus, HA emerges as a promising candidate for future research into the role of dietary components in mood regulation, and dynamic and experimental studies are recommended to confirm its efficacy and therapeutic relevance.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest. The funders had no role in the study design, data collection, analysis or interpretation, writing of the manuscript or the decision to publish the results.

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